

ECONOMETRICAL APPROACH OF TURNOVER OF GOODS IN AZERBAIJAN'S TRANSPORT SECTOR

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Abstract

This study investigates the contribution of air transport to Azerbaijan's economic growth, especially the relationship between income and air cargo turnover. The study examines regression analysis, stationarity tests, and model diagnostics like the Durbin-Watson statistic, CUSUM stability test, and heteroskedasticity tests as a part of econometric analysis using annual data from 1996 to 2024. The results show a high positive correlation between income and air cargo turnover, the importance of regression model parameters and parameter stability. The analysis also shows that a significant increase in air transport happened after 2013, with a major rise between 2020 and 2024 because of infrastructure improvements and the post-pandemic recovery in foreign trade. Despite temporary declines, such as external shocks like COVID-19 and geopolitical concerns, the long-term trend is still good. In summary, Azerbaijan's air transport sector has been essential for improving economic performance of the country.

This study examines the turnover of goods in sea transport in Azerbaijan using econometric tools from 2001 to 2024. The research goals to evaluate the relationship between turnover of goods and expenditure of goods with some econometrics methodology, simple linear regression model and it supported by tests including importance of regression model, F-statistics and t-statistics, CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares, for defining errors heteroscedasticity analyses used White test. The statistical results indicate that model is unimportant and unstable. These limitations suggest that the current model does not adequately capture the economic dynamics of sea transportation. Also, study concludes that maritime transport plays a crucial role in the country's trade system, more advanced econometric models, methodologies and additional variables such as - price of oil, transport modes conditions and the most influential factor is the political relations between countries.

This study examines the turnover of goods in pipeline transport in Azerbaijan using econometric tools from 2000 to 2024. This research emphasizes the role of Azerbaijan in today's global oil and gas market, development of pipeline transportation and its outcomes, integration of Azerbaijan into European market, the substantial role of key routes of pipelines. It evaluates the relationship between income from transportation in the transport sector and expenditure on goods transportation in the transport sector with some econometrics methodology. It uses regression analyses, stability and heteroskedasticity tests to show importance and stability of models.

Keywords: Sea transport, air transport, pipeline transport, income, expenditure, regression equation, importance of regression model, CUSUM test, White test, Dickey-Fuller test.

Introduction

The transportation system helps foster economic growth, increase efficiency and production, and promote environmental sustainability. In other words, transportation is critical to logistics and the efficient flow of goods and resources. In fact, transportation and logistics often contribute significantly to a country's GDP while also providing national security. Efficient transportation systems can increase a country's or region's competitiveness by cutting transportation costs, expanding connectivity, and improving the speed and dependability with which goods move. Azerbaijan played a crucial role in the historic Silk Road, facilitating trade between China and Europe for centuries. The picture remains the same now. Azerbaijan serves as a balancing power between geopolitical heavyweights such as the European Union (EU) and Russia, while also strengthening economic links with China through projects such as the Belt and Road Initiative. However, in the middle of rising geopolitical tensions and economic rivalry, transportation in Azerbaijan appears to be stalled, defying aspirations and expectations for stable and upward development. Air transport contributes significantly to Azerbaijan's economic growth. The Baku-Tbilisi air route opened in

1924, providing the foundation for air travel in Azerbaijan. As the republic gains independence and expands its connections with other nations, this field is growing quickly. Azerbaijan used to have air connections with the CIS, however these days, our aircraft travel to numerous European and Asian nations.

Baku is home to the republic's most significant airport. By building a new facility on September 30, 1999, passenger services were improved and there were more options for aircraft departures. The airports at Ganja and Nakhchivan were also rebuilt.

Helicopter landing zones and the republic's airports in Ganja, Nakhchivan, Yevlakh, Sheki, Lankaran, and other places are crucial to air travel.

Aviation is used to maintain contacts with the mountainous regions, transport cargo and emergency transportation of patients, as well as to combat parasites in agriculture.

With the increase in the world population, the demand for goods and services is increasing day by day. Also, the integration of countries leads to the expansion of international transport routes. In today's world, it is impossible to imagine global trade without international modes of transport. These modes of trade are: sea, air, rail and pipeline. In this article, we will mainly focus on the Sea transport mode. Maritime transport

plays crucial role in international global trade systems. According to the UNCTAD Around 80% of the volume of international trade in goods is carried by sea, and the percentage is even higher for most developing countries. Ports are the milestones of that industry in all over the world. The busiest of these ports handle over 50 million tons of cargo annually, while approximately 15 ports manage more than 200 million tons of goods per year in terms of cargo turnover. Example for most famous ports in the world are Rotterdam, Shanghai, and Singapore. For the Azerbaijan Caspian Sea has of great importance for maritime trade. Despite having no access to the oceans, Azerbaijan is able to trade large quantities of goods with countries that have access to the Caspian Sea. The oldest and largest port in the Caspian Sea is located in the Baku Bay. It is called "The Port of Baku". This port is mentioned in historical documents dating back to the 16th century. It should be noted that in order to effectively use the transit opportunities of Azerbaijan, the newest and largest Baku International Sea Trade Port (BMMTP) and Free Trade Zone were built on an area of 400 hectares, 65 km south of the center of Baku, in the village of Alat. The port of Baku includes the main cargo terminal, container terminal, Dubende oil terminal (capacity up to 12 million tons), ferry terminal and passenger terminal. The ferry terminal serves the following directions: Baku-Turkmenbashi - Baku, Baku - Aktau - Baku, Baku - Iranian ports - Baku. Also, sea lines such as Baku - Makhachkala, Baku - Astrakhan, Baku - Anzali, Baku - Aktau and Baku - Mangistau are used for the transportation of oil, oil products, food and forest materials. Azerbaijan also plays an important role on the Great Silk Road. The Baku International Maritime Trade Port, plays a key role for freight from China to Europe, as well as an attractive corridor for traffic from Europe to Central Asia. The port is an integral part of the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route (TMTM), developed within the framework of the new "Great Silk Road" project. Its significance in cargo transshipment further increased with the launch of the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars (BTK) Railway on 30 October, 2017.

In today's world, pipelines are considered as cost-effective means of delivering gas and oil to consumer nations. Azerbaijan has demonstrated throughout its history that it possesses significant oil and gas reserves. Historically, Azerbaijan oil was primary goal of the Nazi Germany during world war II and forming the core of the Soviet energy system. In October 1991, Azerbaijan gained independence and since that, the country's oil industry has been in decline due to the decreasing oil production and overworked technology that required immediate investments and improvements. The oil production continued to drop until 1996 and it hit a level of almost 9 million tons annually (Gorkhmaz Askerov, 2008)

One of the most important economic decisions made in the early years of Azerbaijan's independence was the "Contract of the Century," which was signed on September 20, 1994, between the Republic of Azerbaijan and foreign oil firms. This contract represented a significant turning point in the country's economic development because it made it possible for Azerbaijan to

sell its energy resources on the international market and contributed significantly to the growth of the nation's economy. The significant Azeri-Chirag-Gunashli (ACG) and Shah Deniz fields in the Caspian Sea are two of Azerbaijan's petroleum and natural gas reserves that had the potential to play a major role in the global oil and gas market. Additionally, deal turned into crucial tool for attracting foreign investment and boosting Azerbaijan's economic growth.

The construction of major export infrastructure, especially the Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan pipeline (BTC), which became a key route for delivering Caspian oil to global markets, was one of the agreement's primary outcomes. The pipeline begins at the Sangachal Terminal, travels through Georgia, and ends at Ceyhan Port in Turkey, which is located in the Mediterranean. The BTC pipeline improved Azerbaijan's political and economic independence, eliminated its reliance on Russian export routes, and established the nation as a key European energy hub.

Azerbaijan has also launched several main pipeline routes to diversify its energy exports and reduce dependence on a single corridor. Among the first significant oil export routes that gave access to Black Sea ports were the Baku-Novorossiysk and Baku-Supsa pipelines. Furthermore, the South Caucasus Pipeline is essential for delivering natural gas to regional markets. These pipelines, which connect Azerbaijan to Europe, are part of the larger Southern Gas Corridor, which also includes projects like the Trans-Anatolian Natural Gas Pipeline and the Trans Adriatic Pipeline.

Today, Azerbaijan's oil and gas reserves are still able to maintain their relevance. The Russia-Ukraine war is a clear example of this. Azerbaijan emerged as one of the key alternative energy suppliers in this context. It has strengthened relations with Europe and confirmed the role of Azerbaijan in oil and gas market. The geopolitical importance of Azerbaijan and the Southern Gas Corridor only grows as Europe looks to diversify away from Russia. Another example of this is the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) on Strategic Partnership in the sphere of Energy, which was signed on July 18, 2022, between Azerbaijan and the EU. It should be mentioned that the goal of the new Memorandum is to increase Azerbaijan's gas exports to the EU through the Southern Gas Corridor by 2027 (Fidan Namazova, 2023).

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between the turnover of goods and income of goods in air transport in Azerbaijan during the period of 1996-2024?
2. What is the relationship between the turnover of goods and the expenditure of goods in maritime transport in Azerbaijan during the period 2001-2024?
3. What is the relationship between income of goods and the expenditure of goods in pipeline transport in Azerbaijan during the period 2000-2024?

Research Hypotheses

- H₁: There is a relationship between the turnover of goods and income of goods in air transport.
- H₂: There is a relationship between the turnover of goods and expenditure of goods in maritime transport.

H₃: There is a relationship between income of goods and expenditure of goods in pipeline transport.

Methodology

In this study, econometrics approach is used, specifically regression analysis, stationarity tests, model diagnostics, stability and heteroskedasticity tests. Simple linear regression model and importance of regression model is analyzed. Heteroskedasticity is examined by using the White test and for defining stationarity of time-series Dickey-Fuller test is used.

Literature review

G. Ahmadova’s (2009) “Improving Air Transport Infrastructure Management” claims that modernizing the air transport complex of Azerbaijan is crucial for the implementation of the innovative model for economic growth in the country. The report explores outstanding problems with airport and ground-handling infrastructure, their current state and their management of them. By way of systems-based and economic analysis, the author argues that an increase in air facilities is necessary to protect territorial integrity and security, as well as foster socio-economic growth. Various suggestions for more effective management of infrastructure are made.

Niftiyev, I. (2024) ‘Multidimensional assessment of transportation sector’s performance: Nonparametric analysis of the Azerbaijani economy’ indicated that the positive trajectory of the maritime, aviation, and road transport sectors underscores their potential contributions to economic growth and development. He emphasized that these sectors, displaying increasing performance potential over the years, are likely to foster trade, facilitate logistical operations, and enhance connectivity, all of which are pivotal for a thriving economy.

Imamoglu and Imanov (2008) reach the conclusion that the commercial air transport activities consume large amounts of fossil fuel and CO₂ emissions, which in general deteriorate the environment. The effect of national income, energy consumption and use of fossil fuel on environmental quality is investigated by the authors, considering the ARDL model with data covering a period of 108 quarters from 1992 to 2014.

Their empirical results validate the presence of EKC for Azerbaijan.

Gorkhmaz Askerov’s (2008) “OIL AND GAS PIPELINE STRATEGY OF A LANDLOCKED COUNTRY: CASE OF AZERBAIJAN” claims that Azerbaijan’s strategic location and balanced foreign policy have enabled it to diversify its pipeline transport routes and reduce dependence on particularly Russia. As a result, it has gained greater advantages over its energy exports and strengthened its economic position in energy market.

Tuncay Babalı’s (2005) “IMPLICATIONS OF THE BAKU-TBILISI-CEYHAN MAIN OIL PIPELINE PROJECT” discusses that BTC pipeline re-shaped regional energy politics by reducing reliance on Russia and creating alternative export routes driven primarily by geopolitical interests.

Huseynova Nurana’s (2025) “THE AGREEMENT OF THE CENTURY – AN INTERNATIONAL PROJECT THAT TURNS AZERBAIJAN INTO AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE GLOBAL WORLD ECONOMY” shows that “The Contract of the Century” had a big role in transforming Azerbaijan into a strong, diversified economy while launching major projects like “BTC” and “Southern Gas Corridor”.

Fidan Namazova’s (2023) “UKRAINIAN WAR AND ITS IMPACT ON SOCIA-ECONOMIC SITUATION IN AZERBAIJAN” highlights the role of Azerbaijan as a major alternative energy source especially for European market after Ukrainian conflict.

Empirical results and findings

Section 1 analyzes the econometrics indicators for the period 1996-2024 based on official data from the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

$$INCOME = 988.757393985 * TURNOVER_OF_GOODS_AIR_ + 35101.5460531$$

When turnover of goods by air increases 1 unit, it means that income will increase 988,75 units

Table 1.

Result of Regression analysis

Dependent Variable: INCOME
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 03/31/26 Time: 09:20
 Sample: 1 29
 Included observations: 29

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
TURNOVER_OF_GOODS__AIR_	988.7574	64.88750	15.23803	0.0000
C	35101.55	82023.55	0.427945	0.6721
R-squared	0.895832	Mean dependent var		788637.0
Adjusted R-squared	0.891974	S.D. dependent var		1072216.
S.E. of regression	352408.1	Akaike info criterion		28.44944
Sum squared resid	3.35E+12	Schwarz criterion		28.54374
Log likelihood	-410.5169	Hannan-Quinn criter.		28.47897
F-statistic	232.1974	Durbin-Watson stat		0.971568
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

$R^2 = 0.8$, it means that turnover of goods approximate income is strong.

F-statistics = 232 F-table and $\text{Prob}(F\text{-statistic}) = 0 < \text{Prob}(0.05)$, it means that regression model parameters are important.

Turnover of goods t-statistic $\text{Prob} = 0 < 0.05$, it means that regression model parameters are important.

C t-statistic $\text{Prob} = 0.6 > 0.05$, it means that regression model parameters are unimportant.

Durbin-Watson stat = $0.9 < 2$, it means that autocorrelation is positive.

Graph 1. Result of CUSUM test

In the graph, main line doesn't intersect border line, it means that regression model parameters are stable.

Graph 2. Result of CUSUM of Squares test

In the graph, main line doesn't intersect border line, it means that regression model parameters are stable.

Table 2.

Result of White test

Heteroskedasticity Test: White
Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity

F-statistic	41.11211	Prob. F(2,26)	0.0000
Obs*R-squared	22.03298	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0000
Scaled explained SS	29.99510	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0000

F-statistic (Prob) = 0 < Prob(0.05), it means that regression model errors are heteroscedastic.

Table 3.

Result of Dickey-Fuller test

Null Hypothesis: D(TURNOVER_OF_GOODS) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=6)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-4.519002	0.0067
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.339330	
5% level	-3.587527	
10% level	-3.229230	

Dickey-Fuller test statistic(Prob) = 0 < 0.05 and Dickey-Fuller test statistic value = -4.5, less than test critical values (1% ,5%, 10% levels), it means that time-series are stationary.

Section 2 analyzes the econometrics indicators for the period 2001-2024 based on official data from the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

We can see here **Simple Linear Regression** equation between Turnover of Goods (manats) and Expenditure of Goods (manats)

$$\text{EXPENDITURE_OF_GOODS} = -20.6754655358 * \text{TURNOVER_OF_GOODS} + 233354.806109 \quad (1)$$

The regression equation (1) is analyzed The Slope (C1 = -20.675): This represents a negative correlation. For every 1-unit increase in the turnover of goods, the expenditure on goods is expected to decrease by approximately 20.675 units, holding all else constant. $R^2 = 0.367$ it is more than 0.3 means that Turnover of Goods approximate Expenditure is middle. F-statistics = 12.89 and Prob(F-statistics) = 0.00 < Prob(0.05) it means that regression model parameters are important Turnover of Goods t-Statistic (Prob) = 0.001 < Prob(0.05) it means that regression model parameters are important .C (constant) Prob) = 0.00 < Prob(0.05) it means that , regression model parameters are important. Durbin-Watson stat. = 0.409 is less than 2 , it means that Autocorrelation is Positive

Graph 3. Result of CUSUM test

Graph 3 is shown **Main line (blue line)** does intersect with **Border lines (red lines)**, it means that regression model parameters are **unstable**.

Graph 4. Result of CUSUM of Squares test

Graph 4 result is shown that, main line (blue line) does intersect with Border lines (red lines), it means that regression model parameters are unstable.

Table 4.

Result of White test

This table is represented Regression Model Errors are **Homoscedasticity** or **Heteroscedastic**

Heteroskedasticity Test: White

Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity

F-statistic	3.981392	Prob. F(2,21)	0.0342
Obs*R-squared	6.598358	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0369
Scaled explained SS	3.873241	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.1442

F-statistic (Prob) = 0.0342 < Prob(0.05) it means that regression model errors are **Heteroscedastic**.

Section 3 analyzes the econometrics indicators for the period 2000-2024 based on official data from the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Estimation Command:

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LS EXPENDITURE_TO_GOODS_TRANSPORTATION_THOUSAND_MANATS
INCOME_FROM_TRANSPORTATION_IN_THE_TRANSPORT_SECTOR_THOUSAND_MANATS C
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Estimation Equation:

```
EXPENDITURE_TO_GOODS_TRANSPORTATION_THOUSAND_MANATS =
C(1)*INCOME_FROM_TRANSPORTATION_IN_THE_TRANSPORT_SECTOR_THOUSAND_MANATS
+ C(2)
```

Substituted Coefficients:

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EXPENDITURE_TO_GOODS_TRANSPORTATION_THOUSAND_MANATS =
0.252342059306*INCOME_FROM_TRANSPORTATION_IN_THE_TRANSPORT_SECTOR_THOUSAND
_MANATS - 22645.5132799
```

We can see here simple linear regression equation between income from transportation in the transport sector (thousand manats) and expenditure to goods transportation (thousand manats) in the transport sector.

The Slope (C1) is 0.25, it represents a positive correlation. For every 1-unit increase in income from transportation, expenditure to goods transportation is expected to increase approximately 0.25 units.

Table 5.

Result of regression analysis

This table shows importance of regression model (income from transportation in the transport sector is independent variable (X) and expenditure to goods transportation (Y))

Dependent Variable: EXPENDITURE_TO_GOODS_TRANSPORTATION__T
 HOUSAND_MANATS
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/21/26 Time: 10:52
 Sample: 2000 2024
 Included observations: 25

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
INCOME_FROM_TRANSPORTATION_IN _THE_TRANSPORT_SECTOR__THOUSA ND_MANATS	0.252342	0.020281	12.44240	0.0000
C	-22645.51	39580.02	-0.572145	0.5728
R-squared	0.870651	Mean dependent var		371286.2
Adjusted R-squared	0.865027	S.D. dependent var		323267.3
S.E. of regression	118764.1	Akaike info criterion		26.28428
Sum squared resid	3.24E+11	Schwarz criterion		26.38179
Log likelihood	-326.5536	Hannan-Quinn criter.		26.31133
F-statistic	154.8134	Durbin-Watson stat		1.040951
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

R² (R-squared) is 0.87. This number is higher than 0.7 means that income from transportation approximate expenditure to goods transportation is strong.

F-statistics is 154.8 and Prob(F-statistics) is 0 and this number is less than Prob(0.05) means that regression model parameters are important.

Income from transportation (Prob) is 0 and it is less than Prob(0.05) it means that parameter is important.

C (constant) Probability is 0.57 and it is more than Prob(0.05), it means that parameter is unimportant.

Durbin-Watson statistics is 1.04 and it is less than 2, it means that autocorrelation (regression model errors) is negative.

Graph 5. Result of CUSUM test

These tables show Cusum and Cusum square tests. They define stability between parameters.

In this graph, Blue line (main line) does not intersect with red lines (border lines), it means that regression model parameters are stable.

Graph 6. Result of CUSUM of Squares test

In this graph, Blue line (main line) intersects with red lines (border lines), it means that regression model parameters are unstable.

Table 6.

The result of White test

This graph shows homoscedasticity or heteroscedasticity of regression model errors with White test

Heteroskedasticity Test: White
Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity

F-statistic	4.230743	Prob. F(2,22)	0.0279
Obs*R-squared	6.944413	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0310
Scaled explained SS	7.289017	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0261

F-statistic (Prob) is 0.0279 and this number is less than Prob(0.05) it means that regression model errors are heteroscedastic.

Table 7.

Result of Dickey-Fuller test

This graph presents stationary or non-stationary of time series.

Null Hypothesis: D(INCOME_FROM_TRANSPORTATION_IN_THE_TRANSPORT_SECTOR_THOUSAND_MANNATS) has a unit root

Exogenous: None
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=5)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-2.965385	0.0049
Test critical values:		
1% level	-2.669359	
5% level	-1.956406	
10% level	-1.608495	

In here, Dickey-Fuller t-statistic is (-2.97) and it is less than critical values (1%, 5%, 10%) and Dickey-Fuller t-statistic Prob (0.0049) is less than Prob(0.05), it means that time-series are stationary

Conclusion

Based on data analysis, the air travel sector in Azerbaijan has grown significantly in recent years. The data of the goods turnover from 1996 to 2024 are examined in this study. In the 1990s and early 2000s, the turnover of commodities was low; however, after 2013, it started to rise. Due to the development of logistics infrastructure, the construction of new international airports, and the revival of international trade after the pandemic, the biggest growth occurred between 2020 and 2024.

In this study, we examined the regression equation, importance of regression model, CUSUM test and heteroskedasticity tests. Results show that the regression model parameters are important and autocorrelation is positive. In CUSUM test, we have analyzed that regression model parameters are stable.

In conclusion, we can state that the turnover of goods in Azerbaijan's transportation industry has increased favorably. There are diminishing directions that are impacted by negative factors like COVID-19 or political events, even though there are fluctuations in the tables that result from positive factors like new projects (BTC, TAP, TANAP) and increasing energy consumption. It is obvious that Azerbaijan had a major impact on the global energy system, particularly for European nations, which benefited Azerbaijan's economic and political might.

This study examined the relationship between the turnover of goods and the expenditure of goods in maritime transport in Azerbaijan over the period 2001–2024 using a simple linear regression model and a set of econometric diagnostic tests. The empirical findings indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between the variables, as confirmed by the F-statistic and t-statistic results ($p < 0.05$). The R^2 value of 0.367 suggests a moderate level of explanatory power, meaning that turnover of goods explains a noticeable portion of the variation in expenditure. However, despite statistical significance, the model reveals several important econometric limitations. The negative coefficient implies an inverse relationship between turnover and expenditure, which is not fully consistent with economic expectations and may indicate model misspecification or omitted variables. In addition, the Durbin-Watson statistic points to the presence of positive autocorrelation in the residuals, violating the classical regression assumptions. Furthermore, the results of the CUSUM and CUSUM of squares tests demonstrate that the model parameters are unstable over time, suggesting structural changes within the maritime transport sector. The White test confirms the presence of heteroscedasticity, indicating that the variance of the error terms is not constant and reducing the efficiency of the estimates. Overall, while the regression model is statistically significant, it does not provide a fully reliable representation of the economic relationship between turnover and expenditure in Azerbaijan's maritime

transport sector. These findings suggest that more advanced econometric approaches, along with the inclusion of additional explanatory variables such as fuel costs, infrastructure development, and international trade conditions, are necessary to obtain more accurate and robust results. Despite these limitations, maritime transport continues to play a strategically important role in Azerbaijan's economy, particularly through its integration into regional and global trade corridors.

Overall, the study discusses the role of Azerbaijan in global energy market and mention about substantial role of these energy resources in economic growth of Azerbaijan. Also it describes role of infrastructure developments and investments to pipeline transportation and its effects to the income from pipeline transport. The country's strategic response to global events, such as the Russia-Ukraine war, has further reinforced its importance as a reliable energy supplier to Europe.

This research analyzed the development and economic role of pipeline transportation in Azerbaijan over 2000-2024 using econometrical analysis. The regression analysis revealed a strong and positive relationship between income from transportation and expenditure on goods transportation in the transport sector. With an R-squared value of 0.87, the model demonstrates a high explanatory power, indicating that changes in transportation income significantly influence expenditure levels. The statistical significance of the independent variable further supports the reliability of this relationship. Augmented Dickey-Fuller test confirms that the time series data is stationary, which strengthens the validity of the regression results. Nevertheless, future research could improve the model by addressing additional variables to capture broader economic dynamics.

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